

Assessment of study skills and its correlation with academic performance of First BDS students

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Abstract –

Background-

First BDS is the year where the students first enter into the professional college from their high school learning. It is a challenging and independent mode in their life. In the beginning of this year, everything is new, start from the college to study subjects and exam pattern. However, by crossing all the hurdles, it is a challenge to the students to show their good academic performance. Every Student has their own way of learning. They apply their study skill while learning but... are they using it correctly? It is a big question because of transition from the school environment to the professional college, the students may find out to difficult to deal with it. So to help out the students of first BDS, the present study explored their study skills and also correlated it with their academic performance.

Aim-

To evaluate the study skill and its correlation with academic performance among first BDS students.

Materials and Methods-

A questionnaire based cross sectional study was conducted among first BDS students. Total 99 students of First BDS of VSPM's Ranjeet Deshmukh Dental College and Research Centre, Nagpur was selected. Out of 99 students; 93 were female and 6 were male students. The mean age of the study participants was 19 years. A close ended; University of Houston questionnaire consisting of 64 questions of specific areas of study skills in eight domains was used. During the routine class; the questionnaire was distributed and got filled by all willing First BDS students of batch 2021-2022

Results-

Time management and procrastination, study aids and note taking, motivation and attitude and writing skills showed statistically significant correlation with academic performance.

Conclusion- The present study findings revealed adequate study skills among majority of the study participants. Four study skills showed significant correlation ($p < 0.05$) with academic performance.

Key words- *study skills, academic performance, first BDS students, questionnaire based study, assessment.*

Introduction-

“Teachers open the door, but you must enter yourself”

-Ancient Chinese proverb

All over the world in our education system, teachers have incorporated different innovative teaching methods to improve the teaching. The ultimate aim of every teacher is ...how the student will get benefit from it. However, the point to be noted that... Do the students understand it? Are they retaining this information in their mind? How are they revising it and reproducing it during the examination? etc. The answers to all this question is how the students learn the study material when they are studying at home. So...Do our students are aware about the details of their study skills? If they know, are they aware which one is strong and which needs improvement?

Study skills or study strategies are the useful methods of learning. Study skills are different skills, which includes the process of organizing and grasping new information, retaining that information, or dealing with it during assessments.

Study skills are distinct techniques that can be learned, in a relatively short period and is applied to each field of study. Study skills can also be explained as any skill, which improves a person's ability to study, retain and reproduce the information, which assist in and secure good grades in exams [1].

After the high school training, when the student enters into professional college, they found everything new starting from the college to study subjects and exam pattern. Some students get adapted with it very easily some may found difficulty. In addition to get adjustment with these factors, they have to show their good grades in the academics

also. For that, they should know how they are studying. How they can improve their study skills to improve their academic performance.

Aims and objectives-

The aim of the present study was to evaluate the study skill and its correlation with academic performance among first BDS students of VSPM's Ranjeet Deshmukh Dental College and Research Centre, Nagpur (Formerly known as VSPM Dental College and Research Centre, Nagpur) and the objectives were

- To evaluate the study skill of first BDS students
- To evaluate the study skill and its correlation with academic performance of first BDS

The Null hypothesis of the present study was there is no correlation between the study skills and academic performance of first BDS students.

Material & methodology:

Study design- A cross sectional study was designed.

Study setting- This study was conducted at VSPM's Ranjeet Deshmukh Dental College and Research Centre, Nagpur (Formerly known as VSPM Dental College and Research Centre, Nagpur). Institutional ethical committee approval was obtained with dated July16, 2022 and reference number (IEC/VSPMDCRC/06/2022).

Study size- Total 99 students of First BDS of VSPM's Ranjeet Deshmukh Dental College and Research Centre, Nagpur was selected.

Tool Used:

The questionnaire consisted of two parts, first part consist of demographic characteristics i.e. gender, age and second part consist of 64 specific questions.

University of Houston questionnaire consisting of 64 questions of definite areas of study skills in eight domains of time management & procrastination, concentration/ memory, study aids/note taking, test strategies, organizing & formation processing, motivation & attitude, reading and selecting the main idea, and writing skills (each domain with 8 questions). The questions was graded with a 4 degrees scale as never, sometimes, usually or always, from 1 to 4 score. The maximum score was 32 and the lowest one is eight in each domain. Higher scores in each domain indicate the more favorable position of the student in that domain [2].

Study Procedure-

During the routine class; the questionnaire was distributed and got filled by all willing First BDS students of batch 2021-2022.

Statistical methods-

To get the result; the data was inserted in MS-excel and descriptive statistical measures were calculated in MS-excel 2010 and Chi square test was applied to find correlation between individual study skill and academic performance by using SPSS version 2020.

Results and discussion-

All the first BDS students of batch (2021-2022) filled the questionnaire. Out of 99 students; 93 were female and 6 were male students.

The questionnaire was scored for each student in which it is found that majority of the study participant was having adequate score of their study skill. In three study skills namely time management & procrastination where 18(18%), motivation & attitude 13(13%) and writing skills 19 (19%) of the students were found in below 20 score as compare to other study skills.

On the contrary; more than 28 score was found among 28 (28%), 31 (31%) , 27 (27%) and 31 (31%) of the study participants in concentration & memory, study aids/note taking, organizing & processing information and reading & selecting the main idea type of study skill respectively as compare to other study skills.

While comparing the mean score of eight different study skills, highest mean score was found to be of study aids/note taking and least mean score was found in writing type of study skill.

The detailed descriptive analysis is depicted in Table 1.

To find out the significant correlation between individual study skill and academic performance; a chi square test was applied by using SPSS software of version 2020. The p value of significance is set at <0.05 level.

Out of the eight study skills; four study skills namely time management & procrastination, study aids/note taking motivation & attitude and writing skills were found to be statistically significant while correlating them with student's academic performance.

As the p value of significance of these four study skills while correlating with the academic performance of the students was coming below 0.05 level; the null hypothesis of the present study was rejected.

The detailed chi square test value results of all study skills are depicted in Table 2.

The present study focused on evaluating the study skills of First BDS undergraduates as they are new for the this professional course and might find difficulties while studying these new subject in a new environment.

Academic performance is defined as “knowledge achieved or skills learned in school subjects usually evaluated by test scores or by grades allotted by teachers or by both” [3]. The ultimate goal of any educational course is to clear it's academic exam of that year and enter into next grade, for that how the students are reproducing their gained knowledge is very important as academic performance is considered as a chief analysts for assessing the quality of education and understanding of the students [4]. In the present study, the authors not only given acknowledgement to the students about their study skills but also correlated their study skills with academic performance.

In the previously conducted study among undergraduate dental students, the authors had found; mean score of writing study skill had the lowest score (2.22 ± 0.49) and the study habit of information-processing (2.79 ± 0.45) had the highest mean score and standard deviation [5] while in another literature; lowest mean score of time management study skill (19.96) and highest mean score was found in motivation type of study skill [6], while in another published literature it is found that note taking, memory, test preparation and time management type of study skills were having more mean score among the students of private medical college [7] and in one another study study aids /note taking, organizing & processing information and test strategies & test anxiety has high mean score [5]. In the present study the lowest mean score was found that of writing skill and the highest mean score was found in note taking type of study skill.

Many of the researches have proven that the one of the most effective factors on academic achievement is regarded as study skills [8-14]. To correlate the study skills and academic performance; many studies have been conducted. In one study, it is found that the note-taking skills, memory skills and time management skills showed significant correlation with academic performance [7] and in another study taking notes while reading, rewriting lecture notes and reviewing lecture notes were associated with good performance [5]. In one another published literature time management and writing skills showed statistically significant correlation with academic achievement [15]. While the present study results showed time management and procrastination, Study aids/note taking, Motivation and Writing skills significant correlation with academic performance.

The good thing about the present study is that; both the teachers and students got aware about the study skill so they both can work on particular domain where the score is coming weak. As already many of the researchers have found that study skill are significantly correlated with academic performance of the student, so it is the prime duty of the teachers to help the students by giving certain tips to improve their study skills or by conducting workshops on improving study skills. As the ultimate goal of both teacher and student is to give good academic results. This has become a very important tool for the students.

Limitations-

The limitations of the present study was due to less number of participants, the result cannot be generalized also the sociodemographic details were not considered for the comparison of the results.

Conclusion-

The present study results can be concluded that there is a adequate study skills among majority of the study participants. Four study skills showed significant correlation with academic performance. It seems that the students are applying their time management skill effectively by avoiding other activities to complete their scheduled planned work and remaining alert all the time. The second study skill where the result has come significant is study aid/ note taking; here the present study participants are not only having habit of making, the lecture notes but they revise and review it regularly which is very good for retaining the knowledge. The third study skills of the present study participants depicts that the students remain quite alert, attentive and regular in their classes. In addition, they take initiative in many group activities of the institute. The fourth study skill of the present study participants showed that the students are very expressive in making their own notes; also, they welcome the suggestion given by their teachers and improve their written work sportingly. While among below average score, maximum number of participants were found in three study skills i.e. time management & procrastination, motivation and writing. For that, appropriate intervention needs to administer to improve their study skills. The educators need to arrange workshops for improving the study skills and keep check on student's behaviour regarding its implementation after all the main aim of the educators and the students is academic success of each student.

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Table 1- **Descriptive** statistical measures of eight study skills-

Sr nos	Study skills	≤ 20	21-28	> 28	Mean	Std. Deviation
		n (%)	n (%)	n (%)		
1	Time management and procrastination	18 (18)	75 (76)	6 (6)	23.34	3.051
2	Concentration/ memory	7 (7)	64 (65)	28 (28)	25.18	3.180
3	Study aids/note taking	8 (8)	60 (61)	31(31)	25.68	3.499
4	Test strategies & Test anxiety	9 (9)	73 (74)	17 (17)	25.05	3.208
5	Organizing & processing information	7 (7)	65 (66)	27 (27)	25.47	2.964
6	Motivation & attitude	13 (13)	74 (75)	12 (12)	25.58	2.949
7	Reading and selecting the main idea	7 (7)	61 (62)	31 (31)	23.86	3.120
8	Writing skills	19 (19)	73 (74)	7 (7)	22.90	3.515

Table 2- Chi square test was applied to find correlation between individual study skill and academic performance

Sr nos	Study skills			Chi square test ($p < 0.05$)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	
1	Time management and procrastination	23.34	3.051	0.001*
2	Concentration/ memory	25.18	3.180	0.630
3	Study aids/note taking	25.68	3.499	0.016*
4	Test strategies & Test anxiety	25.05	3.208	0.155
5	Organizing & processing information	25.47	2.964	0.165
6	Motivation & attitude	25.58	2.949	0.014*
7	Reading and selecting the main idea	23.86	3.120	0.244
8	Writing skills	22.90	3.515	0.009*
*Correlation is significant at < 0.05 level				